

appropriate management decisions.

We set up a trial to determine possible effects of sweep-net sampling on rice yields. IR62, IR64, and IR1917-3-17 were transplanted 20 d after seeding at 25 × 25 cm. Each field was divided into 24 6.25- × 8.3-m plots. Four treatments were replicated six times in a randomized complete block design.

We sampled weekly for 3 consecutive weeks starting at 67 d after transplanting (DT), making 1, 3, or 6 passes through a

Effect on yield of sweep-net sampling for 3 consecutive weeks beginning 67 DT. IRRI, 1987.

Passes through the plot (no.)	Yield ^a (t/ha)		
	IR62	IR64	IR1917-3-17
0	3.7 a	3.8 a	3.2 a
1	3.2 ab	3.6 a	3.2 a
3	3.2 ab	3.7 a	3.0 b
6	3.0 b	3.6 a	2.8 b

^a Av of 6 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 10% level by DMRT.

plot. The sampler made 10 sweeps/pass.

There was no significant difference in yields of IR64 from the different sweep-net pass patterns (see table). However, sterile spikelets at harvest should be evaluated. From 0 to three passes through IR62 did not significantly affect yields, but 6 passes did. Yield of IR1917-3-17 decreased with 3-6 passes. One pass through the field did not significantly affect yield of any variety. □

Leaffolder (LF) outbreak in Haryana

G. A. Qadeer, S. P. Arya, and O. S. Tomer, Central Surveillance Station, India Ministry of Agriculture, Karnal, Haryana, India

LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) has been observed in most rice-growing areas of Haryana, but its incidence has been below the economic threshold. Our regular pest monitoring surveys now show that since 1983, LF has started to cause significant damage to the rice crop. A severe outbreak was observed during 1987 kharif (Jul to mid-Oct).

We surveyed extensively during 1987 to monitor LF in the major crop areas—Kurukshehra, Karnal, Ambala, Jind, Sirsa, and Sonapat. Peak incidence was in mid-September when rice was at the panicle emergence stage. In 13 of 145 villages surveyed, 1-5% leaves were found damaged; in 28 villages, 5-25%; in 44 villages, 50%; and in 60 villages, more than 50%. Populations ranged from 2 to 20 larvae/hill. PR106 and Basmati 370 were the most affected rice varieties.

The nitrogenous fertilizer recommendation for these ricefields is 100-140 kg N/ha. Excessive application of nitrogenous fertilizer, coupled with indiscriminate application of granular pesticides and other formulations, could have resulted in resurgence.

Average monsoon rainfall is 500-750 mm during kharif. But in 1987 kharif, unprecedented drought Jul-Oct could have affected the insect population. □

Acoustic signal-producing organ of brown planthopper (BPH)

Z. T. Zhang and W. Z. Kong, Plant Protection Department, China National Rice Research Institute; J. L. Gao and T. H. Shao, Central Laboratory, Jiangsu Agricultural College, China

Prior to copulation, both male and female adults of the rice BPH communicate primarily by means of

acoustic signals emitted by specialized signal-producing organs. We investigated the structure and function of those organs.

The signal-producing organ (possessed only by the adults) is situated on both sides of the juncture of the pterothorax and abdomen (Fig. 1). It is composed of a sclerotizing coxata and a petal-like sclerite extended in the front of the third sternopleuron (the first and second sternopleuron are underdeveloped and invisible). The underside

1. I. Acoustic signal producing organ of *N. lugens* in lateral view. II. Coxata in posterior view. III. Petal-like sclerite in the front of third sternopleuron in anterior view, arrow points upward. IV. Flaky processes on the top of coxata. A = petal-like sclerite, B = coxata, C = a hole before coxata, D = the top of coxata covered with flaky processes, E = pterothorax, F = trochantin, G = femur, H = underside of the sclerite.